

Assessment of Transformational Leadership Characteristics for the Leaders of ECSD Design + Build

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ABSTRACT: The main aim of this study is to determine the level of characteristics of the leaders of ECSD Design + Build in relation with the eight characteristics of a transformational leadership. A quantitative method used to analyze the current study. 30 workers were involved in this study to assess their leaders which consist of one architect and two engineers. The results revealed that the highest value level out of eight characteristics was performer which averaged to 6.64. The highest trait for the architect leader was being energetic which results to a score of 6.74 while both engineers produced the highest characteristic which is being a performer and it produces a score of 6.63 and 6.98, respectively.

KEYWORD: Transformational leadership

I. INTRODUCTION

In the fast-paced, competitive corporate environment of today, the commercial world has become more global, which has had a crucial influence in leading the project team to success project development and efficient communication with the project sponsor and vendors. Currently, construction projects encounter numerous difficulties when it comes to coordination between group, project creator, project clients, and banking industries, builders, and designers. (2013) (Oladipo et al.), highlighted the primary difficulties in construction industries, such the construction of a global learning proficiency, global adaptability, and developing getting ready to join a competitive market. in chronological order maintain and preserve market competitiveness, project. Building is necessary to create a successful team project as a result, the project manager will be in charge of vital in creating a project team that works well.

This study determines the characteristics of transformational leaders of ECSD Design + Build. For the current study, the researcher picked transformational leadership. According to the definition of transformational leadership, this type of leadership fosters the development of leaders who were formerly followers while also bringing about good changes in the social system and the individual. It raises the morale, drive, and productivity of the followers. Contractors are attempting to improve their performance in their domains in light of the increasing rivalry in the construction industry, as well as the high demand from users, limited resources, and lack of environmental awareness (Notgrass, 2013). According to (Beekun, 2012), reasons for

client discontent in the construction sector were investigated in South Africa and numerous factors that affect project performance were discovered, including contractors' lack of skills, conflict, and poor workmanship. According to (Voon, 2011), the involvement of multidisciplinary professions in a project result in project role differentiation, which tends to create unfavorable associations among project participants.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Dynamic and effective leadership is one important characteristic that distinguishes successful organizations from unsuccessful ones in the twenty-first century (Drucker, 1999). It seems vital to develop effective leadership endeavors for the leaders given the rapid, complex, and frequently discontinuous change of work in various industries (Hesselbein and Gldsmith, 2006). Due to the importance of the leadership function, numerous organizations are consequently looking for strong leaders in order to enable the tasks to be completed successfully (Hersey et al, 2001). Even though there are many works and studies on leadership in the management literature, a clear vision of leadership has yet to materialize to adequately serve all business organizations. The five stages of leadership approaches, namely trait, style, contingency, new leadership, post-charismatic, and post-transformational leadership approaches, are acknowledged by Bryman and Parry (2006). Despite the fact that these phases may have different points of view and study periods, they all share a unique definition. The process of influencing members of an organized group to work toward the achievement of a certain goal in a given circumstance is how

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some academics define leadership (Terry, 1960; Tannenbaum et al., 1959; Koontz and O'Donnell, 1959; Stogdill, 1950). There are not enough empirical studies to establish the link between leadership conduct and overall success in project-oriented contexts and associated workgroup situations, despite the fact that the role of leadership has long been acknowledged as a success element for businesses (Kissi et al., 2012; Muller et al., 2012; Yang et al., 2011). According to McDonough (2000), not much work has been done in project-based environments to investigate the relationship between team effectiveness and leadership behavior. Managers have significant leadership challenges in the construction industry, such as managing the workers and dealing with problems like transition teamwork (Toor & Ofori, 2008). Surprisingly, a review of the leadership literature revealed that due to the distinctive, novel, and transient nature of projects' working environment, leadership behavior has no bearing on project success. More research on leadership behavior as well as the environment and

circumstances that might have an impact on the teams working on the construction project is unquestionably required as a result of the problem.

Therefore, this study determines the characteristics of transformational leaders of ECSD Design + Build. According to (Hacker, et al., 2003). Transformational leadership embodies all eight characteristics or traits embraced in the management and leadership sciences (see Figure 1). Transformational leadership calls upon the leader to be capable of envisioning a new future (what can be) while at the same time being analytical about the current reality (what is today). The transformational leader employs and fosters creative thinking (outside the box) while being proficient in the administration of the business (inside the box). He or she is energetic (power within) and knows how to empower others (tapping power in others). Finally, the transformational leader is a results producer and knows how to build community to attain results through many.

Fig 1. Traits of Transformational Leadership

III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

3.1 Research Model

Fig 2. Research Model, by the author, 2022

3.2 Research Hypothesis

H1: The leaders of ECSD Design + Build has a high level of being administrative.

H2: The leaders of ECSD Design + Build has a high level of being analytical.

H3: The leaders of ECSD Design + Build has a high level of being performer.

H4: The leaders of ECSD Design + Build has a high level of being energetic.

H5: The leaders of ECSD Design + Build has a high level of being empowering.

H6: The leaders of ECSD Design + Build has a high level of being creative.

H7: The leaders of ECSD Design + Build has a high level of being visionary.

H8: The leaders of ECSD Design + Build has a high level of being a community-builder.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.1 Design of the Study

The aim of this study is to determine the characteristics of transformational leaders of ECSD Design + Build. A quantitative measure is used to analyze the current study. Each question in the assessment corresponds with one of the eight characteristics of transformational leadership. The questions corresponding with each transformational leadership characteristic are as follows:

Administrative (14 questions)

5, 10, 14, 16, 27, 29, 46, 52, 55, 58, 64, 68, 72, 76

Analytical (12 questions)

11, 18, 20, 25, 31, 38, 45, 57, 78, 82, 84, 87

Performer (13 questions)

1, 2, 3, 7, 13, 15, 32, 43, 54, 59, 83, 85, 86

Energetic (8 questions)

6, 17, 23, 42, 51, 53, 66, 80

Empowering (10 questions)

4, 19, 26, 37, 40, 47, 74, 77, 79, 88

Creative (10 questions)

8, 21, 28, 33, 34, 36, 61, 71, 75, 81

Visionary (10 questions)

9, 22, 30, 35, 39, 48, 49, 62, 67, 70

Community-Builder (11 questions)

12, 24, 41, 44, 50, 56, 60, 63, 65, 69, 73

For each characteristic, total your responses (1–7) for each question and then divide your total by the number of questions for that characteristic. Those with the lowest average score would be your learning opportunities. Consider what action you might take in at least two of the learning opportunity areas and develop a personal improvement plan.

4.2 Sampling size and Target Population

The researcher will select 30 workers under ECSD Design + Build to assess the engineers and architect leaders. The study was carried out at ECSD Design + Build.

V. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Table 1: Transformational Leadership Assessment Survey Result

Leader	Transformational Leadership Characteristics Average						
	Analytical	Performer	Energetic	Empowering	Creative	Visionary	Community- Builder
Architect	6.56	6.31	6.74	5.62	6.47	5.84	5.45
Engineer 1	6.36	6.63	5.67	5.52	5.73	5.90	6.31
Engineer 2	5.48	6.98	6.40	6.12	5.35	6.45	5.20
Mean	6.13	6.64	6.27	5.75	5.85	6.06	5.65

Table (1) shows the results of the assessment survey in this study, participants were the workers of ECSD Design + Build. The architect leader shows high levels in all of the characteristics. Based on the survey, he accumulated an average score of 6.56 for the trait analytical, 6.31 for performer, 6.74 for energetic, 5.62 for empowering, 6.47 for creative, 5.84 for visionary and 5.45 for community-builder. This shows that his strengths are being creative, analytical and energetic, and his traits which includes being empowering and community-builder needs improvement (Hacker, et al., 2003). However, the first engineer leader shows high level results in all of the eight characteristics of transformational leader, an average of 6.36 for analytical, 6.63 for performer, 5.67 for energetic, 5.52 for empowering, 5.73 for creative, 5.9 for visionary and 6.31 for community builder. His strengths are being a performer and analytical, and the traits that needs improvement are being creative and being visionary. Lastly, the second engineer leader shows high level results in all of the eight characteristics of transformational leader, an average of 5.48 for analytical, 6.98 for performer, 6.40 for energetic, 6.12 for empowering, 5.35 for creative, 6.45 for visionary and 5.20 for community builder. His strengths are being a performer and visionary, and the traits that needs improvement are being creative and being a community builder.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The self-assessment survey results were used to analyze the current study. The researchers found out that the highest value out of all the traits for the three (3) leaders is being a Performer. As per the level, both of the respondents show high levels for the eight characteristics.

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